

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF MASS AND DIMENSIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ULTRAVIOLET BALLAST WATER TREATMENT SYSTEM ELEMENTS

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Abstract

The article analyzes the mass and dimensional characteristics of the elements of ultraviolet ballast water treatment systems, which are crucial for ensuring the environmental safety of navigation. In particular, the study examines the impact of system capacity on the space and weight of its components, such as coarse filtration filters, UV reactors, and power supply units. The results demonstrate that with the increase in system capacity, both the linear dimensions and weight of the main elements rise. This allows for predicting mass and dimensional parameters when designing new ships or retrofitting existing ones. The obtained dependencies can also be used for the development of new ballast water treatment systems or the expansion of the range of existing ones.

Keywords: ultraviolet treatment, ballast water, mass and dimensional characteristics, system capacity, area, dimensions, weight, coarse filtration filter, UV reactor.

Introduction. At the current stage of maritime development, the protection of the marine environment from invasive species during ballasting and deballasting operations is a critical issue. According to the International Convention for the Control and Management of Ships' Ballast Water and Sediments [1], starting from September 8, 2024, all commercial vessels engaged in international trade must comply with the D2 standard. This essentially means that ships must be equipped with ballast water treatment systems.

Problem Statement. When designing new ships or retrofitting those in operation, it is essential to consider the space and weight of the ballast water treatment system elements. Given that the most environmentally friendly systems are disinfection systems using ultraviolet (UV) treatment—since they do not produce or introduce chlorine-containing substances—this study investigates the impact of the capacity of ultraviolet ballast water treatment systems on the mass and dimensional characteristics of their elements. Despite numerous studies focused on the effectiveness of ballast water treatment systems [2-6], the influence of system capacity on the mass and dimensional parameters of its individual elements has not been sufficiently studied.

Objective. The aim of this work is to analyze the mass and dimensional characteristics of the elements of ultraviolet ballast water treatment systems and to establish functional dependencies of these characteristics on system capacity.

Materials and Methods. The study utilized statistical data on the mass and dimensional characteristics of elements of ultraviolet ballast water treatment systems obtained from manuals, catalogs, and other informational sources of companies such as AlfaLaval [7], Desmi OceanGuard [8], Wartsila [9], Hyundai [10], Optimarin [11], covering a capacity range from 60 to 3500 m³/h.

The primary methods of analysis included trend line analysis, theoretical analysis, and synthesis of results.

Research results. The main elements of the ballast water treatment system [1, 7-11] include: a coarse filtration filter (32, 40, or 50 μm, depending on the manufacturer), a UV reactor, a control panel, a power supply unit for the UV reactor, and, in some cases [7, 10], a separate cleaning-in-place (CIP) unit for the UV tubes of the reactor. Analysis of sources [7, 8, 9] allowed for the determination of the linear dimensions of key elements of ultraviolet ballast water treatment systems (Table 1).

Table 1

Mass and Dimensional Characteristics of Ultraviolet Ballast Water Treatment System Elements

Model	Q ₀ m ³ /h	Control panel				UV power panel				Filter				UV reactor				
		l, m	b, m	h, m	m, kg	l, m	b, m	h, m	m, kg	l, m	b, m	h, m	m, kg	l, m	b, m	h, m	m, kg	
Wartsila	AQ-125-UV	125	1	0,3	1	110	1,2	0,5	1,4	200	0,8	0,5	2,3	330	0,8	0,5	0,9	125
	AQ-300-UV	300	1	0,3	1	110	1,2	0,5	1,8	350	1	0,7	2,3	510	1	0,7	1,3	285
	AQ-500-UV	500	1	0,3	1	110	1,2	0,5	2	450	1	0,7	3	885	1	0,7	1,3	320
	AQ-750-UV	750	1	0,3	1	110	2x1,2	0,5	2	750	1,3	1,1	3,3	1460	1,2	0,7	1,3	490
	AQ-1000-UV	1000	1	0,3	1	110	3x1,2	0,5	2	1350	1,3	1,1	3,3	1600	1,2	0,7	1,3	490
Desmi	135-340	135	0,38	0,6	0,2	25	0,61	0,59	1,8	262	0,95	0,45	0,45	131	0,78	0,8	0,44	150
	190-340	190	0,38	0,6	0,2	25	0,61	0,59	1,8	262	1	0,45	0,4	192	0,78	0,8	0,44	150
	250-500	250	0,38	0,6	0,2	25	0,61	0,59	1,8	272	1,15	0,5	0,5	288	0,9	0,8	0,45	190
	340-750	340	0,38	0,6	0,2	25	0,61	0,68	2,2	349	1,2	0,5	0,5	322	0,85	0,8	0,52	222
	500-1000	500	0,38	0,6	0,2	25	1,21	0,58	1,8	498	1,3	0,65	0,65	527	0,99	0,8	0,54	331
	750-1500	750	0,38	0,6	0,2	25	1,2	0,7	2,2	677	1,55	0,7	0,7	757	1,03	0,8	0,63	390
	1000-2100	1000	0,38	0,6	0,2	25	1,2	0,7	2,2	788	1,75	0,8	0,8	900	1,1	0,8	0,72	580
AlfaLaval PureBallast	300	300	0,65	0,31	1,1	50	0,9	0,48	2	250	0,49	0,5	1,2	82	0,7	0,7	1,31	250
	600	600	0,65	0,31	1,1	50	1,35	0,61	2	370	0,73	0,72	1,58	241	0,86	0,8	1,4	320
	1000	1000	0,65	0,31	1,1	50	1,35	0,61	2	400	0,77	0,79	1,75	370	1,03	1	1,5	400
	1500	1500	0,65	0,31	1,1	50	2,38	0,61	2	760	0,78	0,79	2,25	480	1,12	1,1	1,48	650

The data showed that: the linear dimensions of the UV reactor range from 0.44 m to 1.5 m, and the weight ranges from 125 kg to 650 kg; the dimensions of the filter range from 0.45 m to 3.3 m, and the weight ranges from 82 kg to 1600 kg. The dimensions of the power supply unit for the UV reactor vary from 0.48 m to 2.38 m, and the weight from 200 kg to 1350 kg. The size and weight of the control panel are practically independent of the system's capacity. The overall trend indicates an increase in mass and dimensional characteristics with an increase in system capacity.

At the same capacity, the weight of some elements, such as the filter and the power supply unit, can

vary by up to 4 times, and the linear dimensions by up to 2 times. This indicates a significant influence not only of capacity but also of other factors: orientation (horizontal or vertical), design features, type of UV lamps used, and specifics of capacity determination (which can differ by a factor of 3 depending on the UV transmittance of water [12]), among others.

Despite these differences, data analysis revealed linear dependencies both for the space occupied by system elements (Fig. 1) and for their weight (Figs. 2 and 3) relative to the ballast water treatment system capacity.

Fig. 1. Dependence of the space occupied by ballast water treatment system elements on system capacity.

Trend analysis showed that the coarse filtration filter and the UV reactor occupy almost the same area, which, on average, increases by 0.7-0.8 m² for every 1000 m³/h of system capacity. The area occupied by the

power supply unit for the UV reactor significantly increases with system capacity, while the control panel remains almost unchanged.

Mass analysis identified significant differences in the weight of coarse filtration filters from different manufacturers (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Change in the weight of the coarse filtration filter depending on the capacity of the ballast water treatment system.

Despite the significant differences in filter weight from various manufacturers at the same system capacity (up to 4 times), there is a clear linear relationship between the filter's weight and system capacity, allowing the prediction of filter weight with further increases in system capacity.

Mass analysis of other elements, such as the UV reactor and its power supply unit, showed smaller fluctuations at the same capacity. A linear relationship is also maintained for these components (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Change in the weight of the UV reactor and its power supply unit depending on the capacity of the ballast water treatment system.

The linear dependencies of the ultraviolet ballast water treatment system elements indicate that increasing the system's capacity is achieved through a proportional increase in treatment elements (UV lamps), leading to a corresponding increase in the power supply unit for these lamps. The capacity increase in the coarse filtration filter is also due to an increase in the filtration area.

Conclusion. The obtained results make it possible to perform a preliminary assessment of the mass and dimensional characteristics of elements of ultraviolet ballast water treatment systems. This contributes to the effective design of new ships or the renovation of existing ones and allows for predicting the size of elements when designing new ballast water treatment systems or expanding the range of existing systems.

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